

Project Title	Blue-Cloud 2026: A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
Project Acronym	Blue-Cloud 2026
Project Number	101094227
Type of project	RIA – Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Starting date of Project	01 January 2023
Duration of the project	42 months
Website	www.blue-cloud.org

D6.2 - Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Education Plan, 2nd release

Work Package	WP6 Outreach, engagement, and education
Task	T6.1 Communication and dissemination pathways
Lead author	Rita Meneses (Trust-IT)
Contributors	Sara Bozzi, Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT), Julia Vera, Angelika Karampourouni (SSBE), De Karaca (EuroGOOS), Anna Silyakova (Hub Ocean)
Peer reviewers	Julia Vera (SSBE) Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)
Version	V1.0
Due Date	30/06/2024
Submission Date	05/07/2024

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	07/06/2023	Rita Meneses (Trust-IT)	Table of Contents
0.2	12/06/2024	Rita Meneses (Trust-IT)	Chapter 1.1 and 2, 4.6, 4.7
0.3	14/06/2024	Sara Bozzi (Trust-IT)	Chapters 7.1, 7.2, 7.3
0.4	14/06/2024	Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Chapter 6
0.5	18/06/2024	Deniz Karaca (EuroGOOS)	Chapter 5
0.6	19/06/2024	Rita Meneses (Trust-IT)	Chapters 1, 4.1, 4.2
0.7	21/06/2024	Julia Vera (SSBE)	Chapter 3
0.8	23/06/2024	Rita Meneses (Trust-IT)	Executive Summary, Conclusion
0.9	27/06/2024	Julia Vera (SSBE), Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Internal review
1.0	05/07/2023	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Integration of comments and final version for upload

Keywords

Blue-Cloud 2026, EOSC, Marine research, Open Science, Website, Social Media, Newsletters, Training

Disclaimer

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094227. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructure
DD&AS	Data Discover and Access Service
DestinE	Destination Earth
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
ESEB	External Stakeholders Expert Board
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
KER	Key Exploitable Result
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices
OTGA	OceanTeacher Global Academy
PCO	Project Coordinator Officer
PMB	Project Management Board
SAC	Scientific and Administrative Coordinator
SB	Steering Board
SDG	UN Sustainable Development Goal
SG	Stakeholder Group
SSO	Single Sign On
TOC	Table of Contents
TSC	Technical and Scientific Committee
VLab	Virtual Lab
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main goal of Blue-Cloud 2026 WP6 is to promote and disseminate the project ambition, on-going activities and Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to the identified list of key stakeholder groups throughout content-rich communication activities, via multi-channel user-centric campaigns. This is done through consistent and content-rich communication activities, by using multiple integrated communication tools. The success of this mission is highly dependent on a continuous interaction with all WPs.

The Blue-Cloud “D6.2 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Education Plan, 2nd release” is an updated version of “D6.1 - Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Education Plan, 1st release” released in March 2023 (M3). **This report documents the results and impact of communication efforts undertaken from January 2023 (M1) to June 2024 (M18)**, which focused on creating awareness about the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, its goals, its ambition and the expected KERs.

This report also defines the communication strategy roadmap for M19-M30 (July 2024 - June 2025). The focus from M19 onwards will be to consolidate the active stakeholder engagement approach for each target group by disseminating the project’s KER to the relevant user communities.

The document is divided in specific sections, listing the results achieved during this first reporting period:

- Section 1 gives an overview of the Blue-Cloud 2026 Community and the engagement with ESEB;
- Section 2 lists the status of the KPIs for outreach and dissemination
- Section 3 updates the stakeholder engagement plan for the next period;
- Section 4 details the implemented actions for the Campaign #2, focused on promoting the Blue-Cloud KERs
- Section 5 lists the communication results from M1-M18 and indicates plans and goals for the next period;
- Section 6 lists the Blue-Cloud peer-reviewed publications
- Section 7 details the implemented actions for the Campaign #3, focused on the Blue-Cloud 2026 Training Academy;
- Section 8 is dedicated to the synergies established so far or otherwise planned, with different, related initiatives and projects;
- Section 9 details the implemented actions for the Campaign #1, focused on generic outreach and dissemination activities (e.g. website, social media, newsletters);
- Section 10 includes a timeline of the Action Plan of activities from M18 till M30;
- Section 11 provides an overall conclusion for the document.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. The Blue-Cloud Community	9
1.1. Engagement with ESEB	12
2. Key Communication, Dissemination & Outreach Performance Indicators	14
3. 2nd release Stakeholders Engagement Plan	17
4. Promotion of the Blue-Cloud KERs (Campaign #2)	19
4.1. Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS)	19
4.2. Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)	23
4.3. Blue-Cloud Essential Ocean Variables (EOV) Workbenches	24
4.4. Blue-Cloud Thematic Virtual Labs	26
4.5. Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030	28
5. Blue-Cloud Events	28
5.1. Blue-Cloud Events	28
5.2. Blue-Cloud at third-party events	44
5.3. Next Blue-Cloud events	47
6. Publications	47
7. Blue-Cloud Training Academy (Campaign #3)	50
7.1. Plans ahead: OTGA training courses	56
1.2. Blue-Cloud’s training academy materials	57
8. Synergies, EOSC & DTO (Campaign #4)	59
9. Main Outreach and dissemination achievements from M1-M18 and future plans (Campaign #1)	62
9.1. Website	62
9.2. Social Media	62
9.3. Communication Kit & Newsletters	67
10. Timeline of Action Plan from M18	70
11. Conclusion	71

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Blue-Cloud VRE Aggregated users by June 2024	9
Figure 2 Increase in Blue-Cloud VRE Aggregated users by June 2024	10
Figure 3 Blue-Cloud 2026 website users by stakeholder category	10

Figure 4 Blue-Cloud European user base (website registered user information)	11
Figure 5 Blue-Cloud Worldwide user base (website registered user information)	11
Figure 6 Interviews with Marco Filippone and Elisa Ravagnan, Blue-Cloud ESEB members	13
Figure 7 – Blue-Cloud 2026 Stakeholder Groups (SGs) and motivation for engagement	17
Figure 8 Blue-Cloud 2026 poster showcased at EMODnet OpenConference 2024 (left) and Poster at EGI 2023 (right)	20
Figure 9 Blue-Cloud 2026 “Optimising FAIRness of federated Blue Data Infrastructures webinar” webinar official image	21
Figure 10 Page dedicated to DD&AS and VRE in the foldable flyer distributed at the UN Ocean Decade Conference	21
Figure 11 Blue-Cloud 2026 “FAIR Data Principles 2 Making Marine Data FAIR: FAIR assessment of marine data & information” agenda	22
Figure 12 Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE Open Info Day Official Image (left) and VRE Hands-on Workshop (right)	23
Figure 13 Blue-Cloud 2026 Poster presented at EOSC National Tripartite Event in Belgium in April 2024, and related SoMe post on X	24
Figure 14 Workbenches video interviews on Blue-Cloud 2026 YouTube channel	25
Figure 15 Page dedicated to the Workbenches in the “Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs & in support of Workbenches Sustainable Development Goals” booklet	26
Figure 16 Vlabs video interviews and Info session on Blue-Cloud 2026 YouTube channel	27
Figure 17 Official image of Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at European Marine Day 2023	29
Figure 18 Tweets about Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at European Marine Day 2023	29
Figure 19 Social media posts about Blue-Cloud at European Marine Days 2024	30
Figure 20 Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at the European Marine Days 2024 - event page	31
Figure 21 Tweets about Blue-Cloud joint-session at the EOSC Symposium 2023	32
Figure 22 Event page and banner for Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at the Open Science Fair 2023	34
Figure 23 Tweets about Blue-Cloud joint-workshop at the Open Science Fair 2023	35
Figure 25 Official image of Blue-Cloud Joint Satellite Event at the United Nations Ocean Decade Conference	36
Figure 26 Full room at the World Trade Center for the Blue-Cloud Joint Satellite Event	37
Figure 27 Social Media Posts about Blue-Cloud joint-satellite event at the United Nations Ocean Decade Conference 2024	38
Figure 28 Social Media Posts promoting Blue-Cloud booth at the conference	40
Figure 29 Official image of IMDIS (left) and list of organisers (right)	41
Figure 30 Group photo at the EOSC Coordination meeting 2024	41
Figure 31 Cover of the video realised for the DOF High level event and now available on Youtube	43
Figure 32 Sara Pittonet Gaiarin presenting the Blue-Cloud demo at DOF 2024 - image ©Bernal	

Revert/BR&U	44
Figure 33: Promotional banner for the Special Issue of the International Journal of Data Science and Analytics launched by Blue-Cloud	49
Figure 34 - Examples of graphic banners for social media	63
Figure 35 - Examples of posts for X	64
Figure 36 - Examples of posts for LinkedIn	65
Figure 37 - LinkedIn Newsletter	65
Figure 38- LinkedIn Carousels	66
Figure 39 - Videos available on Blue-Cloud YouTube channel	67
Figure 40 - Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs and Workbenches Booklet	69
Table 15 - Newsletters produced as of M18	70
Figure 41 Communication timeplan from M18 on	71

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1 Agenda of Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at the European Marine Days 2023	30
Table 2 Agenda of Blue-Cloud Joint break-out session at the EOSC Symposium 2023	33
Table 3 Agenda of Blue-Cloud Joint workshop at the Open Science Fair 2023	35
Table 4 Agenda of Blue-Cloud joint-satellite event at the United Nations Ocean Decade Conference 2024	39
Table 5: List of third party events that Blue-Cloud 2026 partners attended	47
Table 6 Blue-Cloud 2026 papers and conference proceedings by M18	48
Table 7: List of webinars organised under the Training Academy	51
Table 8 Agenda of the FAIR Data Principles 1 webinar	52
Table 9 Agenda of the webinar “Optimising FAIRness of federated data discovery and access service and underpinning Blue Data infrastructure”	52
Table 10 Agenda of the FAIR Data Principles 2 webinar	54
Table 11 - training materials developed by M18	58
Table 12 - Synergies established by Blue-Cloud by M18	61
Table 13 - Social Media Followers as of M18	63
Table 14 - Communication Kit items	68

1. The Blue-Cloud Community

Blue-Cloud 2026 has grown a consolidated community of members (over 1.700 members, plus 2.990+ social media followers and 359 newsletters subscribers) who are interested or actively engaged in leveraging its services to advance marine research and innovation, in support of EU policy objectives and a more sustainable Blue Economy. This is the result of a coordinated and continuous communication effort by Blue-Cloud 2026 partners, who continuously cooperate to support the promotion of the Blue-Cloud portfolio of assets.

A Single Sign On (SSO) procedure (leveraging Keycloak technology) was introduced to align registration of users across the public website and the Blue-Cloud open science platform on D4Science, the platform offered via the [Blue-Cloud Gateway](#) which makes the **services and Virtual Laboratories available**, as well as with the Data Discovery and Access service. This allows a better mapping of Blue-Cloud users, who are asked to register on the public website and provide additional, non compulsory information on their profile, affiliation, country, gender and other details useful to ensure a correct analysis and monitoring of the user base. This also facilitates the management of user privacy consent, via a unique Privacy policy (GDPR compliant) which users are asked to accept when registering to the Blue-Cloud website¹. The Blue-Cloud community is composed of the almost 1.700 members registered on D4Science.

Blue-Cloud Gateway Aggregated VRE Users

	2023-01	2023-02	2023-03	2023-04	2023-05	2023-06	2023-07	2023-08	2023-09	2023-10	2023-11	2023-12	2024-01	2024-02	2024-03	2024-04	2024-05	2024-06
Blue-Cloud Gateway	1015	1066	1130	1174	1250	1322	1362	1380	1392	1412	1439	1461	1497	1545	1559	1639	1675	1719
Running Delta		51	64	44	76	72	40	18	12	20	27	22	36	48	14	80	36	44

Figure 1 Blue-Cloud VRE Aggregated users by June 2024

¹ See D1.2 Data management plan for further reference

Figure 2 Increase in Blue-Cloud VRE Aggregated users by June 2024

According to the data gathered from the 685 users who registered via the website since March 2023, when the SSO procedure was in place, 55% of the community members who provided this information come from “Scientific, research & academia”, followed by “Blue-data infrastructures and e-infrastructures” with almost 20% and 4% from SMEs, Industry in the Blue Economy.

Figure 3 Blue-Cloud 2026 website users by stakeholder category

Most of the contacts listed in the Blue-Cloud community database are based in Europe, but the project was also able to bring on board individuals from other countries (e.g USA, Australia, Morocco, Indonesia).

Figure 4 Blue-Cloud European user base (website registered user information)

Figure 5 Blue-Cloud Worldwide user base (website registered user information)

NB: affiliation, country, gender are not compulsory information and therefore not available for all users.

1.1. Engagement with ESEB

The External Stakeholders Expert Board (ESEB) provides high level guidance on strategy and policy and leverage of their relevant cross-sectoral networks. At the moment the ESEB has 12 members from different geographical locations and with distinct backgrounds.

Name	Affiliation	Country	Community
Lijing Cheng*	Institute of Atmospheric Physics	China	Ocean research
Othman Dekkaki	Université Mohammed V de Rabat	Morocco	Ocean research
Marco Filippone	Fugro Germany Marine GmbH	Germany	Blue Economy
Luciano Gaido	Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics	Italy	EOSC
Sara Garavelli	CSC	Finland	EOSC
Hernan Garcia*	US National Oceanographic Data Center of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	USA	Ocean research
Sheila JJ Heymans	European Marine Board	Belgium	Blue Economy
Jaume Piera	Institute of Marine Sciences	Spain	Citizen science
Peter Pissierssens	IODE	Belgium	Ocean research
Elisa Ravagnan	NORCE Norwegian Research Centre	Norway	Ocean research
Marc Taconet	FAO's Fisheries and Aquaculture Division	Italy	Ocean research
Toste Tanhua	GEOMAR Helmholtz Center for Ocean Research Kiel	Germany	Ocean research

Since the beginning of Blue-Cloud2026, a close liaison with ESEB members has been put in place. A total of **three info sessions**, of 90 minutes long, were organised, from which 2 were online (6 September 2023 and 13 May 2024) and one which took place during the project General Assembly in November 2024 (Rome, Italy). These sessions have been useful to provide updates of the project outcomes and collect feedback and strategic advice on the future steps and directions Blue-Cloud 2026 should consider for the next months. In addition, ESEB members attended the Blue-Cloud 2026 online General Assembly in May 2024. ESEB advice and suggestions have been gathered in a summary report (November 2023) and meeting minutes (May 2024), shared with the Blue-Cloud steering board and made available to the entire consortium on D4Science repository.

Members have also been involved in communication/dissemination activities, by promoting Blue-Cloud 2026 events within their networks. At this moment, 2 experts recorded **video interviews** for Blue-Cloud 2026, where they explained how their expertise can help Blue-Cloud 2026 endeavours. The interview are available via the [Interviews playlist](#) in the Blue-Cloud 2026 Youtube channel.

Marco Filippone

Marco Filippone, Chief Hydrographer & Operations Manager, FUGRO Germany Marine

Marco Filippone is Chief Hydrographer and Operations Manager at Fugro Germany Marine GmbH. He is a certified hydrographer, Cat. A certified surveyor, with a MSc in "Marine and Nautical science" from the Italian Naval Academy and Pisa University and second level post degree in "Marine Geomatics" from Genoa University. Just after retiring from the Italian Navy with the rank of Lieutenant (NATO OF-2) he obtained a PhD in system engineering from Genoa University studying "water column acquisition and automatic processing technique". As IHO Cat. A certified surveyor he is involved in large seafloor mapping programs and hydrographic developments.

Elisa Ravagnan

Elisa's main interests are inter- and cross-disciplinary approaches to environmental challenges. She has more than 20 years of experience in environmental modelling and statistics. She has been leading and participating in many national and international projects and industry financed projects in aquaculture and marine sciences. Currently Elisa is the coordinator of the H2020-BG-08-2019 ASTRAL: All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture and the Co-leader of the Nordic Centre of Excellence SUREAQUA (Funder by NordForsk).

Recent projects include: holistic assessment of aquaculture sustainability, development of supporting tools for marine spatial planning (AquaAccept, coordinator, Research Council of Norway), Modelling environmental and socio-economic effects of climate changes and man-made pollution on aquaculture (CII-CAS, coordinator, RFF), Multivariate assessment and spatial modelling in INFRAIA- JERICCO-NEXT, task leading on data management as well as engaging with stakeholders in H2020-BG-04 I-FISHIENCI (Aquaculture 4.0), aquaculture footprint analysis in ERA-Net COFASP ECOAST. I was a member of the Rogaland County reference group (Norway) for the Aquaculture Regional Plan.

Figure 6 Interviews with Marco Filippone and Elisa Ravagnan, Blue-Cloud ESEB members

2. Key Communication, Dissemination & Outreach Performance Indicators

During its first 18 months, Blue-Cloud 2026 has further grown and consolidated a community of members who are increasingly eager to participate in the development and uptake of Blue-Cloud 2026 services, which will contribute to advance research and support a more sustainable Blue Economy. The achievement of these results was possible thanks to a coordinated and continuous communication effort by Blue-Cloud 2026 partners, who cooperated to support the promotion of the Blue-Cloud 2026 portfolio of results.

Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Targets		
	M12	M42	Today (M18)
Website			
N° sessions per month	1000	3,000	1,367 (total 16.398)
N° New Blue-Cloud 2026 services published in the EOSC Marketplace ²	-	5	0 (Virtual Labs still being developed)
Communication Activities/Materials			
N° Newsletters	-	18	6
N° Interviews	-	10	12
N° Blue-Cloud TV	-	1	1
N° videos on Blue-Cloud TV (Short pitch-style videos and interviews with project partners, ESEB, activists & influencers)	1	>40	21
N° views on Videos	300	1,500	1,778
N° of views in sponsored videos	-	20,000	N/A
N° Scientific papers/publication published in Open Access & peer-review magazines and journals	-	5	3

² The EOSC Marketplace is encompassing a consistent revision linked to the Procurement of the EOSC EU Node. Thus this KPIs will have to be reassessed in light of the positioning of Blue-Cloud as an EOSC Node.

Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Targets		
	M12	M42	Today (M18)
N° Online cross-domain factsheets for expansion	-	>5	0
N° Surveys	-	2	1
Blue-Cloud Training Academy N° materials available in the online Training catalogue	-	200	12
Blue-Cloud Training Academy N° trained participants	-	500	428
N° Roll-up banners, posters	3	8	8
N° Press Releases	1	5	1
Average number downloads per resource on ZENODO	-	300	56
N° downloads on ZENODO of VLab Factsheet	-	700	558
N° printed copies & online downloads of factsheet Roadmap & policy briefings	-	5,000	1349
Social Media			
N° total of social media followers across platforms	3000	5,000	2.990+ Social media followers (1.700 Twitter + 1.060 LinkedIn + 231 YouTube subscribers)
Events & Webinars			
N° Webinars on Ocean Literacy	-	3	0
N° Info sessions & course on EOVS workbenches		3	2
N° Webinars on Online VRE	-	2	1
N° Online Trainings courses	-	12	5
N° Webinars to DDAS and the innovations introduced		2	1
N° Webinars on VRE, DDAS & EOVS workbenches		11	2

Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Targets		
	M12	M42	Today (M18)
N° Online Training Course on best practices for FAIR data principles		3	2
N° Annual Impact Events		3	0
Average participants per webinar organised	-	40	143
N° Hackathon		1	0
N° Hackathon participants	-	120	0
N° Policy & DTO Task Force Workshops	-	3	1 meeting in Toulouse, Participation at the DO 2024
N° 3rd party events where Blue-Cloud is promoted	-	40	40
N° participants in the Final Event	-	300	0
Stakeholders			
N° Blue-Cloud Community users	-	>3000	1.719
N° Blue-Cloud Followers across platforms	3,000	5,000	2.990+ Social media followers (1.700 Twitter + 1.060 LinkedIn + 231 YouTube subscribers)
N° DDAS, VRE & EOVS Data Analytics sessions per month	-	3,000	2,540
N° DDAS, VRE & EOVS Data Analytics jobs per month	-	5,000	650
N° ESEB Members	-	10	12
N° New synergies with external initiatives		>10	27
N° EU countries engaged	-	27	33

3. 2nd release Stakeholders Engagement Plan

The implementation of Blue-Cloud 2026’s Stakeholder Engagement Plan (SEP) 1.0 during the first 18 months of the project has contributed to consolidating and further growing the Blue-Cloud 2026 community, as described in the previous section.

Figure 7 – Blue-Cloud 2026 Stakeholder Groups (SGs) and motivation for engagement

Following SEP 1.0, and its specification of targeted Stakeholder Groups (SG - see Figure 6), during the first 18 months of the project priority has been given to establishing stakeholder interactions with stakeholder groups 1, 2, 3 and 4. Blue-Cloud 2026 has significantly kick-started dialogue with relevant EOSC projects and digital twinning initiatives, the latter including through active participation in the [Digital Ocean Forum 2024](#) (Brussels, 12-13 June 2024).

An updated version of the SEP (SEP 2.0) was released in June 2024, establishing priorities for the next 12 months of the project (June 2024 - June 2025), namely:

- As Blue-Cloud’s Core Services, demonstrators and work benches continue to make progress in accordance with the project work plan, interactions with **stakeholder groups 1-4** will continue to be prioritised. Such interactions will be geared at onboarding feedback on the value proposition of the different services being tested and/or rolled out, and to inform their respective **Exploitation Plans**, which will be finalised by the end of 2024.
- Building on initial conversations with Projects that offer potential for establishing synergies with Blue-Cloud (e.g., CLIMAREST), or that plan to make use of Blue-Cloud’s existing core services (e.g., AQUARIUS), additional targeted interactions will be sought to identify and plan concrete, joint activities (e.g., participation in the Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon). These interactions will also seek to gather input and feedback on Blue-Cloud 2026’s Exploitation Plan, and to inform the scope and direction of planned consultations with wider communities towards shaping a new, updated

version of the **Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030**. Stakeholder consultations will be launched in December 2024.

- Likewise, interaction with **EOSC projects** (i.e., FAIR-EASE, AI4EOSC, iImagine) and **communities** will be intensified (including via participation to relevant symposiums and events), with a view to gain further insight on current developments, as well as preparing an effective consultation on **Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030**.
- **With respect to SG#5 SMEs, industry and the Blue Economy**, the liaison partner is HUB Ocean who works with private companies under the mandate of sharing industrial data with science and general public through [the Ocean Data Action Coalition — HUB Ocean | Dedicated to Unlocking Ocean Data](#), and [Ocean Decade Corporate Data Group](#) - where HUB Ocean delivers on the Biodiversity and MetOcean use cases ([How Industrial Ocean Data can fill Scientific Data Gaps - Ocean Decade](#)) with the final goal to produce a guideline for industrial ocean data sharing. This group aims for releasing and sharing of industry data and in support of research underpinning Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). HUB Ocean is aiming for facilitating this group and being an intermediary in the process of receiving industry data and transforming it into more structured data resources which can be made available for users. HUB Ocean overtime has developed a cloud-based Ocean Data Platform which facilitates ingesting ocean data sets and structuring these for discovery, access, and analytics. This platform is offered as an instrument towards the offshore industry and to the Ocean Decade Corporate Data Group. HUB Ocean is also interested in passing on ingested and structured industry data for uptake in established data management infrastructures, such as operated at global level (GBIF, ODIS, OIH) and regional level, such as EMODnet (via SeaDataNet, EurOBIS , .), NOAA, and others. These data centres then could elaborate the recieved data by additional QA-QC and formating for fitting their systems and standards. For Blue-Cloud 2026 HUB Ocean could achieve a flow of more industry data, that then can be made available to Blue-Cloud users (such as VLabs) at level 1 status, from the Ocean Data Platform, and in a later stage as a follow-up at level 2 status through Blue-Cloud BDIs, that are feeding the Blue-Cloud VRE users through the Blue-Cloud DD&AS and its Beacon instances.

4. Promotion of the Blue-Cloud KERs (Campaign #2)

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Education Plan, 1st release identified the key assets that will be at the core of the promotion and outreach campaigns. They are:

- Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS)
- Virtual Research Environment (VRE)
- Essential Ocean Variables (EOV) Workbenches
- Thematic Virtual Labs
- Roadmap to 2023
- Blue-Cloud Training Academy

A specific set of activities is being implemented to disseminate these assets and the related Key Exploitable results (KERs), to support their uptake and accessibility by users, educate a new generation of marine data practitioners and IT experts via training courses/guidelines, assess user experience and validation mechanisms, as well as boost multi-disciplinary cooperation.

The activities performed so far to promote Blue-Cloud 2026 KERs and the mid-term results achieved are detailed in the following sections.

4.1. Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS)

The Blue-Cloud (DD&AS) service has been showcased at several third-party events, highlighting the ease of data access and data discovery across different marine research infrastructures. For instance, at the EMODnet Open Conference 2023 (Oostende, Belgium), a poster³ demonstrated how Blue-Cloud offers simplified access to EMODnet data collections through the DD&AS (as well as the VRE and Vlabs). At the EGI2023⁴ event (Poznań, Poland) a presentation on DD&AS was organised, along with a showcase of a poster. A poster was also showcase in the same month, during the “Oceans 2023” conference⁵ in Ireland.

³ https://blue-cloud.org/sites/default/files/2023-10/PosterA4_October2023_V3_WEB.pdf

⁴ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/blue-cloud-egi-2023>

⁵ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/oceans-2023>

Figure 8 Blue-Cloud 2026 poster showcased at EMODnet OpenConference 2024 (left) and Poster at EGI 2023 (right) Besides showcasing the project at research focused events, the tool was also promoted at policy focused ones, such as the ESFRI-EOSC Policy Workshop on "FAIR Data Productivity and Advanced Digitalization"⁶.

The DD&AS was promoted on webinars from the Blue-Cloud 2026 Training Academy, entitled "Optimising FAIRness of federated Blue Data Infrastructures webinar"⁷, which had 88 registrations. It promoted the architecture and approach for the Blue-Cloud DD&AS, as well as how BDIs are managing their networks of data originators in order to provide harmonised and FAIR discovery and access to their collected data resources, using and promoting best practices and standards.

⁶ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/esfri-eosc-policy-workshop-fair-data-productivity-and-advanced-digitalization>

⁷ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/optimising-fairness-federated-data-discovery-access-service-and-underpinning-blue-data>

Figure 9 Blue-Cloud 2026 “Optimising FAIRness of federated Blue Data Infrastructures webinar” webinar official image

A foldable flyer⁸, with a dedicated page for the DD&AS (also for the VRE and Vlabs) was created to be distributed at the UN Ocean Decade Conference⁹ in April 2024 (Barcelona, Spain) and the “The Data we need for the Ocean we care for - Satellite event” organised there, to promote the service to the worldwide audience that attended the conference.

Figure 10 Page dedicated to DD&AS and VRE in the foldable flyer distributed at the UN Ocean Decade Conference

As part of the Blue-Cloud Training Academy, in April 2024 the webinar “[FAIR Data Principles 2 | Making Marine Data FAIR: FAIR assessment of marine data & information](#)” recruited 75 delegates, to show them

⁸ <https://blue-cloud.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/BLUECLOUD2026%20Booklet%20Mar24.pdf>

⁹ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/2024-ocean-decade-conference>

how Blue-Cloud 2026 services support data FAIRification. In detail, there was a presentation by Tjerk Krijger, MARIS, on the Blue-Cloud data federation approach, and few presentations where Blue-Cloud federated data infrastructures such as EurOBIS Biology, EMODnet physics and EuroArgo demonstrated how they are making their data interoperable with the Blue-Cloud VRE.

Agenda		
Tuesday 23 April 2024; 16.00 CEST		
Chair: Sara Pittonet Gaiarin , Trust-IT Services and Blue-Cloud Coordinator		
Time	Session	
16:00 - 16:10	Welcome & introduction	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin , Blue-Cloud Coordinator
	Overview of the Blue-Cloud Data Federation approach	Tjerk Krijger - Project engineer at MARIS
Session 1: Blue-Cloud Common Metadata Profile: state of the art from Blue-Cloud federated BDIs		
<i>Examples of Blue-Cloud 2026 Data Infrastructures working towards FAIR assessments and FAIR Implementation Profiles for marine data</i>		
16:10 - 16:20	Making EurOBIS Biology metadata interoperable with Blue-Cloud VRE	Katrina Exter , VLIZ
16:20 - 16:30	EMODnet physics integration with Blue-Cloud	Antonio Novellino , ETT
16:30 - 16:40	EuroArgo semantic artefacts	Thierry Carval , iFremer
Session 2: M2M Semantic interoperability in Europe		
<i>Examples of other initiatives in Europe working on FAIR assessment of marine and earth science data</i>		
16:40 - 16:50	FAIR EVA: Bringing institutional multidisciplinary repositories into the FAIR picture	Fernando Aguilar Gómez , CSIC - Spanish National Research Council
16:50 - 17:00	FAIR Connect: Open Access publishing platform of good practices for professional FAIR-Data stewardship	Barbara Magagna , GO FAIR Foundation
17:00 - 17:10	Setting up the EarthPortal, the ontology and vocabulary repository dedicated to Earth sciences	Guillaume ALVISET , DataTerra
17:10 - 17:20	Insights from EuroGoos Data Management practices	Thierry Carval , iFremer
17:20 - 17:45	Q&A, closure and next steps	

Figure 11 Blue-Cloud 2026 “FAIR Data Principles 2 | Making Marine Data FAIR: FAIR assessment of marine data & information” agenda

4.2. Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)

A [VRE and VLabs Info Day](#) was organised in March 2023, to show how to use the VRE, as well as to demonstrate a practical example of how the thematic Virtual Labs work and what services are available for resume and exploitation by external users. The purpose of the session was to provide marine researchers across different sectors with ways for collaborative Open Science within the Blue-Cloud platform.

Later in the same year, in June 2023 (Heraklion, Crete, Greece) a [VRE Hands-on workshop](#) was organised, with the scientific and technical staff working on the Blue-Cloud 2026 VLabs and WorkBenches developments. This was an important event where VLabs and WorkBenches developers brought real examples (algorithms/methods) to implement in their workflows with the support of the Blue-Cloud VRE team during the workshop. [A post event report published on the Blue-Cloud website](#) provides highlights on the main outcomes of the event.

Figure 12 Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE Open Info Day Official Image (left) and VRE Hands-on Workshop (right)

A more complete course on the VRE is expected to be organised by the end of 2024 within the remit and in close collaboration with the OceanTeacher Global Academy (OTGA).

Concerning the promotion at third-party events, the VRE was promoted in several different events to reach distinct audiences, through presentations and posters (e.g. EGI 2023, EOSC National Tripartite Event in Belgium, IMDIS 2024, amongst others).

Figure 13 Blue-Cloud 2026 Poster presented at EOSC National Tripartite Event in Belgium in April 2024, and related SoMe post on X

4.3. Blue-Cloud Essential Ocean Variables (EOV) Workbenches

A total of three data-intensive Workbenches (WB) for selected Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) are being developed and tested in Blue-Cloud 2026. Ocean and data scientists will implement efficient workflows that allow them to harmonise, validate and qualify large and various in situ data sources, exploiting the blue analytical services available in the Blue-Cloud VRE.

- Ecosystem-level EOVs
- Eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen
- Physics: temperature & salinity

Interviews with the teams behind the WB were done, the first one providing an overall overview of the WB, while the remaining two were focused on the Ecosystem-level EOVs and Eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen, having by the time of writing this report almost 200 views.

Figure 14 Workbenches video interviews on Blue-Cloud 2026 YouTube channel

All WBs have also been promoted at key events around Europe (e.g. IMDIS 2024, EMODnet Open Conference 2023, IQuOD 2023 Workshop, EGU2024, etc.).

A **booklet** on “[Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs & in support of Workbenches Sustainable Development Goals](#)” was produced in 2024 and distributed at the “2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference”, at the Blue-Cloud 2026 “The Data we need for the Ocean we care for - Satellite event” and the exhibition booth, to an audience composed by marine experts from around the world. It provided detailed info about the WBs.

Figure 15 Page dedicated to the Workbenches in the “Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs & in support of Workbenches Sustainable Development Goals” booklet

Stakeholder engagement through webinars will continue in the **next reporting period**, more specifically in the second half of 2024, as well as interviews/blogposts when the WBs are further developed. Special focus will be given to them when organising the Blue-Cloud Annual Impact Events, Hackathon and Final Event.

4.4. Blue-Cloud Thematic Virtual Labs

A total of 9 Vlabs are being developed and deployed in Blue-Cloud 2026, making use of the analytical tools and generic services as provided through the VRE, and the data repositories, as made accessible via the DD&AS and through external data services. Each VLab comprises a series of applications for data processing, publishing of data results, and managing computation routines as well as services for collaboration, this way providing open science-friendly working environments for its users to analyse datasets and (re)generate research products:

- Aquaculture Monitor (from Blue-Cloud Pilot);
- Carbon-Plankton Dynamics;

- Coastal currents from observations;
- Fish, a matter of scales (from Blue-Cloud Pilot);
- Global Fisheries Atlas;
- Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe;
- Marine Environmental Indicators (from Blue-Cloud Pilot);
- Plankton Genomics (from Blue-Cloud Pilot);
- Zoo & Phytoplankton EOVI Product (from Blue-Cloud Pilot)s.

Interviews with the leaders of the new Vlabs created within Blue-Cloud 2026 were also organised and published as video pieces, reaching over 300 views on YouTube. An open info session focused on the Vlabs was organised in June 2023, having 94 registrations and over 151 visualisations on YouTube. Vlabs have also been promoted at key events around Europe (e.g. EGU24, EMD 2023, etc.).

Figure 16 Vlabs video interviews and Info session on Blue-Cloud 2026 YouTube channel

The **booklet** “Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs & in support of Workbenches Sustainable Development Goals”, referred already in the previous chapter, has updated factsheets of all Blue-Cloud 2026 Vlabs, which will be made available on ZENODO for further promotion.

Likewise on WB, stakeholder engagement through webinars will continue in the next reporting period, more specifically from 2025, as well as interviews/blogposts when the WBs are further developed. Special

focus will be given to them when organising the Blue-Cloud Annual Impact Events, Hackathon and Final Event.

To conclude, **3 additional VLabs** are being developed jointly with other initiatives (FAIR-EASE and Climarest), an extremely positive outcome where Blue-Cloud 2026 technical novelties can be exploited with other communities from other fields.

4.5. Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030

The Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030 will be a strategic policy document guiding the future development of Blue-Cloud's efforts as a leading component of EOSC for the marine community. Its final version is planned to be presented at the Blue-Cloud Conference taking place at the end of the project.

Activities regarding the creation of this roadmap will be implemented during the following reporting period. An open consultation to collect inputs from key stakeholders will be launched by December 2024, with the first recommendations to be finalised by M36 and, the final Key policy recommendations will be concluded by end of the project.

The final version of the roadmap will be turned into a **graphically designed booklet**, to be later distributed to key-stakeholders from policy and funding bodies, from Europe and beyond. A press-release will be prepared and distributed to key-media channels.

5. Blue-Cloud Events

As part of their dissemination activity of the KERs, Blue-Cloud 2026 is organising distinct events to not only train the community on how to use Blue-Cloud 2026 results, but also to showcase the collaboration work Blue-Cloud 2026 has been doing with other organisations/projects.

5.1. Blue-Cloud Events

Several joint activities were put in place between Blue-Cloud and other initiatives, which took place in different events around Europe, from marine science and policy, to open science.

5.1.1. European Marine Day 2023 and 2024

In these 2 editions of the European Maritime Day, Blue-Cloud organised joint workshops with distinct marine initiatives.

At the [2023 edition, which took place in May at Brest \(France\)](#), Blue-Cloud 2026 organised a 75 minutes workshop with **Technopôle Brest-Iroise, EMODnet, VesselAI and EOOS**. This workshop, entitled "Benefiting from Maritime Data to Drive Marine Innovation", discussed how to ensure these projects are gathering, presenting and using the marine data that is needed to drive European marine and maritime

innovation further. The workshop was organised in two subsections including presentations from the five projects and an open discussion. Patricia Cabreram, VLIZ, represented Blue-Cloud there.

Figure 17 Official image of Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at European Marine Day 2023

Figure 18 Tweets about Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at European Marine Day 2023

Time	Session
16:15	Welcome and introduction - Dick Schaap, MARIS, Blue-Cloud 2026 Technical Coordinator
16:20 minute Lightning talk by each project/initiative	Real-life examples of gathering and using marine data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ocean Hackathon® organised by Campus mondial de la mer, feedback from 7 years of experience - Alice de Joux (Technopôle Brest-Iroise) • The Blue-Cloud thematic Virtual Labs - Patricia Martin-Cabrera (VLIZ) • European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet): The In-Situ Marine Data Service for Europe - Conor Delaney (EMODnet) • VesselAI - Manolis Kaliorakis (MarineTraffic) • The European Ocean Observing System Framework (EOOS) - Inga Lips (EuroGOOS)

Time	Session
16:20 Open discussion Q&A	Gathering data, FAIR data services, and enabling innovation Moderator: Quillon Harpham HR Wallingford, UK, EC Marine Knowledge Expert Group (EMKEG) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Campus mondial de la mer - Technopôle Brest-Iroise - Alice de Joux • Blue-Cloud 2026 - Dick Schaap (MARIS) • European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) - Corine Lochet, SHO • VesselAI - Kimmo Laaksonen (NAPA) • The European Ocean Observing System Framework (EOOS) - Inga Lips (EuroGOOS)

Table 1 Agenda of Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at the European Marine Days 2023

The [European Maritime Days 2024](#) took place in Svendborg (Denmark) and the [Blue-Cloud 45 minutes workshop](#) was organised along with **iMagine, SeaDataNet, and EuroGOOS**. Entitled “Observations to knowledge: Unlocking Ocean Insights” explored the intricate connection between AI technologies, data governance, and policymaking within marine ecosystems, and how collaborative efforts among initiatives can address them. In addition, the audience discovered how they cooperate effectively to avoid duplication in efforts and enhance data quality. These discussions harnessed the collective expertise of the initiatives, reinforcing their position as leaders in advancing operational oceanography for comprehensive marine knowledge. Rita Giuffrida, Trust-IT Services, represented Blue-Cloud there.

Figure 19 Social media posts about Blue-Cloud at European Marine Days 2024

European Maritime Day 2024
 30-31 May 2024 | Svendborg, Denmark

Log in Register

Thursday, 30 May 2024 | 13:30 - 14:45

WS A-3. Observations to knowledge: Unlocking Ocean Insights

In-person Workshop (room Lok 225 - floor 2)
 83 participants

Moderator:

- Rita Giuffrida, Researcher at Trust-IT Services srl and representing Blue-Cloud 2026

Speakers:

- Neil Holdsworth, Head of Data and Information at the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) and representing SeaDataNet
- Inga Lips, Secretary General at EuroGoos, representing the same institution
- Smitesh Jain, Innovation Manager at EGI Foundation and representing iImagine

Description:

The workshop aims to explore the intricate connection between AI technologies, data governance, and policymaking within marine ecosystems, and how collaborative efforts among initiatives like Blue-Cloud, iImagine, SeaDataNet, and EuroGOOS address them. In addition, the audience can discover how they cooperate effectively to avoid duplication in efforts and enhance data quality. These discussions harness the collective expertise of the initiatives, reinforcing their position as leaders in advancing operational oceanography for comprehensive marine knowledge.

4 SPEAKERS

	Inga Lips Secretary General EuroGOOS AISBL		Rita Giuffrida Researcher Trust-IT Services srl
	Neil Holdsworth Head of Data and Information International Council for the Exploration of...		Smitesh Jain Senior Innovation Manager Specialist EGI Foundation

Figure 20 Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at the European Marine Days 2024 - event page

5.1.2. EOSC Symposium 2023

Blue-Cloud 2026 was invited by the EOSC Symposium programme committee to organise a [90 minutes breakout session titled "EOSC contribution to the EU Missions & Partnerships"](#) on 20 September during the EOSC Symposium 2023 that took place in Madrid (Spain), in collaboration with BY-COVID, FNS-Cloud and EOSC4Cancer non-marine projects.

The projects altogether showcased how they have been addressing several challenges related to the EU Missions which aim to create a greener, healthier, more inclusive, and resilient European continent.

Figure 21 Tweets about Blue-Cloud joint-session at the EOSC Symposium 2023

Time	Topic	Speakers
14:00-14:05	Opening	Marieke Willems Senior Project Manager at ELIXIR & BY-COVID
14:05-14.15	The EU mission objectives and Open Science expectations	Marialuisa Lavitrano , Full Professor at the University Milano-Bicocca, EOSC Association
14:15-14.55	What can EOSC offer to the EU Missions? <i>Each project presented how it is contributing to specific objectives of the EU Missions</i>	<i>Blue Cloud 2026</i> Patricia Cabrera , marine biologist at VLIZ BY-COVID & the COVID-19 Data Portal Nadim Rahman Infectious Diseases Project Lead at EMBL-EBI EOSC4Cancer Salvador Capella-Gutierrez , INB Team Lead at Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) FNS-Cloud Karl Presser , founder and managing partner of Premotec
14:55-15:25	Uptake of EOSC in contribution to EU Missions and partnerships <i>Interactive (Spectrum style) discussion with the audience to highlight examples of uptake of EOSC results and outputs within and across EOSC projects in the contribution to the EU Missions</i>	Moderated by Sara Pittonet Senior Project Manager at Trust-IT Trust-IT & Blue-Cloud2026 <i>Blue Cloud 2026</i> Patricia Cabrera , marine biologist at VLIZ Dick Schaap , founder and managing director of the MARIS

Time	Topic	Speakers
		<p><i>BY-COVID & the COVID-19 Data Portal</i> TBC</p> <p><i>EOSC4Cancer</i> Salvador Capella-Gutierrez, INB Team Lead at Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)</p> <p><i>FNS-Cloud</i> Karl Presser, founder and managing partner of Premotec</p>
15:25-15:30	Closure	<p>Sara Pittonet Senior Project Manager at Trust-IT Trust IT & Blue-Cloud2026 & Marieke Willems Senior Project Manager at ELIXIR & BY-COVID</p>

Table 2 Agenda of Blue-Cloud Joint break-out session at the EOSC Symposium 2023

5.1.3. Open Science Fair 2023

A week after the EOSC Symposium in Madrid, Blue-Cloud contributed to the Open Science Fair, which took place also in Madrid (Spain) in September. Along with the FAIR-EASE project, Blue-Cloud organised a [2 hour workshop entitled “Navigating Data Lakes for Earth and Marine Science: Fair Data Management and Service Interoperability in Practice”](#), which stimulated the debate around uptake of FAIR data practices in marine science and neighbouring disciplines, through contributions by key actors such as EuroGOOS and IEEE. [A post event report](#) with the main take-aways of this workshop was produced and published on the Blue-Cloud website, and distributed the Blue-Cloud community.

▶ OPEN SCIENCE FAIR ▶

WORKSHOP ▶▶▶ 27 SEPTEMBER 2023

Navigating Data Lakes for Earth and Marine Science: Fair Data Management and Service Interoperability in Practice

11:30-13:30 CEST - SALA CIUDAD ÚBEDA

eOSC | Blue-Cloud2026 | eOSC | FAIR-EASE

25-27 SEPTEMBER 2023 | MADRID, SPAIN

FECYT | OpenAIRE | U23

#OSFAIR2023

i Blue-Cloud Event
📅 25 September 2023 09:00 – 27 September 2023 13:30
📍 Madrid, Spain

Open Science (also referred to as Open Scholarship or Open Research) is at a crossroads. Implementation and adoption are progressing, with researchers, research institutions, funding agencies, service providers and infrastructures all engaging at various levels. However, different models are emerging which produce a seemingly fragmented ecosystem and achieve small steps on top of traditional scholarly communication system. In order to enable international and interdisciplinary research, we need to ensure interoperability across communities and services while still maintaining our ability to support diversity of workflows and knowledge systems.

Come meet us at our booth during the FAIR!

Navigating Data Lakes for Earth and Marine Science: Fair Data Management and Service Interoperability in Practice

Joint workshop with FAIR-EASE

Figure 22 Event page and banner for Blue-Cloud Joint Workshop at the Open Science Fair 2023

Figure 23 Tweets about Blue-Cloud joint-workshop at the Open Science Fair 2023

Time	Topic	Participant
11:30	Welcome	Rita Giuffrida, Trust-IT Services (Blue-Cloud 2026)
11:35	Interdisciplinary user environments	Patricia Cabrera, VLIZ (Blue-Cloud 2026) Maria Luisa Chiusano, UNINA (FAIR-EASE)
12:05	The Mythical Data Lake	Katrina Exter, VLIZ (FAIR-EASE)
12:05	Interactive polls	
12:30	Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment services for Open Science practices	Massimiliano Assante, CNR (Blue-Cloud 2026)
12:45	Virtual Research Environment (process data As FAIR As Possible)	Marie Jossé, CNRS (FAIR-EASE)
13:00	FAIR Data Discovery and Access	Peter Thijssen, MARIS (Blue-Cloud 2026/FAIR-EASE)
13:15	Q&A and reflections	

Table 3 Agenda of Blue-Cloud Joint workshop at the Open Science Fair 2023

5.1.4. United Nations Ocean Decade Conference

The satellite event “[The Data we need for the Ocean we care for](#)”, co-organised by **Blue-Cloud 2026**, **iImagine**, **DITTO**, **Ocean Best Practices** and **OceanTeacher Global Academy**, was selected by the “United Nations Ocean Decade Conference - Barcelona (Spain)” to take place as part of the main programme of the conference. The 90 minutes event presented cases of success in data sharing practices from European research infrastructures, and how other initiatives can maximise this potential at global level for contributing to the SDGs and the Digital Twins of the Ocean programmes. This event, which was also web-streamed, was a great opportunity for Blue-Cloud to expand further its visibility beyond the European

borders. It counted with over 50 registrations on site, plus attendees that joined the event at the last minute and those that followed the live streaming.

Figure 25 Official image of Blue-Cloud Joint Satellite Event at the United Nations Ocean Decade Conference

Figure 26 Full room at the World Trade Center for the Blue-Cloud Joint Satellite Event

The workshop was opened by European Commission Andreea Strachinescu, head of Unit, Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE), Unit A1: Maritime Innovation, Marine Knowledge and Investment, who have an overview of EU Research and innovation programmes in support of blue economy. **Dick Schaap**, MARIS and Blue-Cloud 2026 Technical Coordinator and **Oriol Prat**, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) and OBSEA, introduced Blue-Cloud2026 and the iMAGINE European projects, with specific insights on data products and scientific applications for marine biology and the fishery domain.

The OceanTeacher Global Academy (OTGA) and the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) of IOC/UNESCO also joined the workshop, with **Rebecca Zitoun**, Co-Coordinator, OBPS UN Ocean Decade Programme: 'Ocean Practices for the Decade' and **Ana Carolina Mazzuco**, OTGA Secretariat, UNESCO IOC Programme Office for IODE who dived into the education and training needs to ensure data management practices and standards are put in place at a global level.

Last but not least, **Alain Arnaud**, Digital Ocean Department, Mercator Ocean International and **Fei Chai**, Xiamen University, China, representatives from the European Digital Twins of the Ocean (EU DTO) Programme and its global counterpart, the DITTO programme, complemented with insights from the

global efforts to build awareness around the ensuring cross-regional data sharing towards the development of digital twins of the ocean.

Blue-Cloud 2026
 1,062 followers
 2mo •

Did you miss yesterday the Blue-Cloud2026, Digital Twins of the Ocean, iMagine, Ocean Best Practices System OceanTeacher Global Academy satellite event for #OceanDecadeConference in Barcelona?

It was a great 90min session to dive in #datasharing of #marinedata stories, with an exciting group of speakers, moderated by Sara Pittonet Galarin: Andreea Strachinescu from European Commission, Dick Schaap from MARIS, Oriol Prat Bayarri from Gandia Campus | Universitat Politècnica de València | Polytechnic University of Valencia, Rebecca Zitoun from GEOMAR Helmholtz-Zentrum für Ozeanforschung Kiel, Ana Carolina Mazzucco from UNESCO/IOC Project Office for IODE, Alain Arnaud from Mercator Ocean International and Fei Chai Xiamen University.

Recording of the event will be online on our event page in the next days! ;)
https://lnkd.in/dX9gRT_p

Figure 27 Social Media Posts about Blue-Cloud joint-satellite event at the United Nations Ocean Decade Conference 2024

Time	Topic	Speakers
17:00 - 17:05	Welcome & Overview	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin , Trust-IT Services & Blue-Cloud 2026 Coordinator
17:00 - 17:05	EU Research and innovation in support of blue economy	Andreea Strachinescu , Head of Unit, Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, A1: Maritime Innovation, Marine Knowledge and Investment - European Commission
17:15 - 17:35	Topic 1: Data Management for achieving UN SDGs	Dick Schaap , MARIS and Blue-Cloud 2026 Technical Coordinator Oriol Prat , Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) and OBSEA
17:35 - 17:55	Topic 2: Best practices and training opportunities for global ocean research	Rebecca Zitoun , Co-Coordinator, OBPS UN Ocean Decade Programme: 'Ocean Practices for the Decade' Ana Carolina Mazzuco , OTGA Secretariat, UNESCO IOC Programme Office for IODE
17:55 - 18:15	Topic 3: Towards Digital Twins of Oceans	Alain Arnaud , Digital Ocean Department, Mercator Ocean International Fei Chai , Xiamen University, China
18:15 - 18:30	Questions & Answers	

Table 4 Agenda of Blue-Cloud joint-satellite event at the United Nations Ocean Decade Conference 2024

Blue-Cloud presence at the event was complemented with a booth at the United Nations Ocean Decade Conference 2024, where the project network with other marine experts around the globe, gave further details of Blue-Cloud 2026 results and distributed communication materials, namely the “Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs & in support of Workbenches Sustainable Development Goals”

Figure 28 Social Media Posts promoting Blue-Cloud booth at the conference

5.1.5. IMDIS

The [International Conference on Marine Data and Information Systems \(IMDIS\) 2024](#) took place in Bergen (Norway) in May 2024 and provided an overview of current information systems addressing the needs of a wide range of users in ocean science. The 2024’s edition is structured around four main sessions: data services and tools in ocean science; technical developments for marine information and data management; marine environmental infrastructures for observation data; and data products, information, and knowledge.

The overall conference was co-organised by Blue-Cloud 2024, along with other relevant marine players: MARIS (Blue-Cloud 2026 Technical Coordinator), SeaDataNet, Institute of Marine Research, IFREMER, iMagine, MEDIN, National Oceanography Center, OGS and IODE. The conference had a call for abstracts for presentations and posters and all the accepted submissions are compiled in the [conference proceedings](#).

Figure 29 Official image of IMDIS (left) and list of organisers (right)

As a note, Blue-Cloud had three poster presentations, along with a generic presentation of Blue-Cloud 2026 mission.

5.1.6. EOSC Coordination meeting 2024

On 20-21 June 2024, the European Commission, represented by DG for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), DG for Communications Networks Content and Technology (DG CNECT), and the European Research Executive Agency (REA), held the 2024 Coordination meeting of EOSC-related projects funded under Horizon Europe.

Figure 30 Group photo at the EOSC Coordination meeting 2024

As one of the EOSC-related projects currently ongoing, Blue-Cloud 2026 was invited to join the event. Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, Trust-IT Services Blue-Cloud Coordinator, and Dick Schaap, MARIS, Technical Coordinator, joined the event, which was opened by Michael Arentoft, Head of the Open Science and

Research Infrastructures Unit at DG RTD, and Karel Luyben, President of the EOSC Association. Arentoft reminded the projects about the dual role of EOSC:

- A policy process to mobilise, align and scale resources to accelerate Open Science, higher quality and productivity and reproducibility in research; and
- A trusted federation of collaborative and autonomous infrastructures combined into a system of systems to enable European researchers to store, share, process, analyse and reuse research digital objects.

The event was the opportunity to showcase current efforts to set up the [EOSC Federation](#), with a presentation of the concept of the [EOSC EU Node](#) and an introduction to the [EOSC Federation Handbook](#) that is being written to describe in detail the characteristics and rules of the EOSC Federation. The opening talks were complemented by two sessions, the first one was an info session on the status of development of the EOSC EU Node, delivered by DG CNECT and representatives of the contractors' consortium. The second session focused on the status of the implementation of the EOSC Federation where DG RTD, EOSC-A, and Volker Beckmann, Co-chair of the EOSC Steering Board, presented activities of the recently launched Tripartite Group aimed at supporting the decision-making by the EOSC Tripartite Governance.

Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, Trust-IT Services Blue-Cloud Coordinator, was invited to be rapporteur for one of the three parallel sessions organised titled "Adding value through the EOSC Federation: Users and Resource environments in thematic communities". The [outcomes of the discussion](#) have been collected by the EOSC Association and published in the [event page](#) on the EOSC Association website.

Blue-Cloud is considered one of the EOSC related projects candidate to become an EOSC Node, part of the EOSC Federation of e-infrastructure services. As an outcome of this meeting, by 31 August 2024 Blue-Cloud 2026 consortium is going to compile the [questionnaire](#) launched by the EOSC Tripartite Group to assess the interest and readiness of potential nodes to join the EOSC Federation.

5.1.7. Blue-Cloud demo at the Digital Ocean Forum 2024

The Digital Ocean Forum is a high-level event, organised since 2022 by the European Commission and by Mercator Ocean International. This year the event was organised under the auspice of the Belgian presidency of the Council of the EU, on 13 June 2024 at the Palace of the Academies in Brussels.

The [European Digital Twin of the Ocean](#) will unlock the door to knowledge and its translation into actions: it is a digital co-creation place at the crossroad of different disciplines. Its purpose is to provide Ocean communities, citizens, coastal actors, scientists, and policymakers worldwide, with actionable knowledge and to support them in their daily decisions and planning, to ensure a healthy and sustainable Ocean.

The [Digital Ocean Forum 2024](#) was the occasion to unveil the prototype of the EU DTO and to showcase what the EU DTO, as a Commission public service, can do for the sustainable development of our blue

economies and the management of our ocean resources, as well as how it contributes to the implementation of the Green Deal and the UN Decade of Science for Sustainable Development. It brought together experts, stakeholders, policymakers and interested citizens in the co-design and co-creation of the European Digital Twin of the Ocean.

Blue-Cloud2026 was selected to [contribute to the European Digital Twin of the Ocean](#), and participated on the 12th of June to the **Digital Ocean Forum Scientific & Technical Workshop**, and on the 13th of June to the main event as an example of platform releasing applications of interest for integration potential with EDITO. **Sara Pittonet Gaiarin**, senior project manager at Trust-IT Services & Blue-Cloud 2026 project coordinator, gave a live demo during the High-Level Event, of how Blue-Cloud Zoo and Phytoplankton EOv demonstrator was used by a team of researchers during the Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2022 to develop an application for the real time assessment of marine megafauna in Marine Protected Areas in the North Atlantic.

The demo was titled "**Unravelling marine food webs towards marine biodiversity conservation, an EDITOBlue Cloud cooperation**" and a video was realised, available on the Blue-Cloud Youtube channel at the link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0c69VO8Gz2U>

Figure 31 Cover of the video realised for the DOF High level event and now available on Youtube

Figure 32 Sara Pittonet Gaiarin presenting the Blue-Cloud demo at DOF 2024 - image ©Bernal Revert/BR&U

5.2. Blue-Cloud at third-party events

During these first 18 months, Blue-Cloud 2026 has actively participated in 40 events covering different project related topics, including Marine Research, Blue Economy, Open Science or Data Management (see table 23). This mass presence at events has allowed the Consortium to already reach the KPI of 40 events attended by the end of the project. Blue-Cloud presence at events was achieved through paper and poster submissions, presentations, as well as participation in panel sessions.

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
1	AqualNFRA kick-off meeting - February 2023	Online	Marine research	Presentation

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
2	Ocean data hour - low cost tech and citizen science - February 2023	South Africa	Marine research	Presentation
3	Economist Impact - World Ocean Summit & Expo - February 2023	Portugal	Ocean health, industry strategies	Panel Discussion
4	From data interoperability to data spaces in the aquaculture domain - February 2023	Online	Aquaculture Data Management	Presentation
5	MARCO-BOLO Kick-off meeting - March 2023	France	Marine Biodiversity	Presentation
6	Workshop on Ocean Health & Observation - April 2023	Online	Policy Making	Presentation
7	EGU2023 - April 2023	Austria	Geoscientists	Presentation (by ESEB member)
8	Ocean Data Hours - Enabling tools for citizen science in ocean data collection - May 2023	USA	Marine research	Presentation
9	Benefiting from Maritime Data to Drive Marine Innovation at EMD 2023 - May 2023	France	Marine research	Joint Workshop
10	EOSC National Tripartite Event Italy - June 2023	Italy	Policy & Open Science	Presentation
11	OCEANS 2023 - June 2023	France	Maritime professionals	Presentation & Poster
12	Ocean Data Hours - Climate change and sustainability: talk to scientists - June 2023	Denmark	Marine Research	Presentation
13	Science – Industry workshop on Ocean Biodiversity Data - June 2024	Online	Marine Research and Industry	Presentation
14	EOSC Coordination meeting - June 2023	Belgium	Policy & Open Science	Networking
15	EGI Conference 2023 - June 2023	Poland	Scientific communities, computing and service providers	Presentation & Poster
16	Open and FAIR environmental data for societal benefits, an ENVRI-FAIR policy event - June 2023	Sweden	Environmental Research Infrastructures	Presentation
17	The Ocean Race Grand Finale - Ocean Data Week - June 2023	Italy	Marine Research	Presentation

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
18	IQuOD group meeting - July 2023)	Online	Climate Data quality and Management	Presentation
19	FNS-Cloud Final Event - September 2023	Belgium	Food Nutrition data management	Presentation
20	EOSC Symposium 2023 - September 2023	Spain	Policy & Open Science	Joint-session
21	EuroSea Symposium on Ocean Observing and Forecasting - September 2023	France	Marine Research	Panel discussion
22	Open Science FAIR 2023 - September 2023	Spain	Open Science	Joint Workshop, booth
23	EuroGOOS Conference 2023 - October 2023	Ireland	Marine Research	Presentation
24	Stakeholders2cOdesign: Towards impactful stakeholder engagement in the Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters - October 2023	Belgium	Marine Research	Networking
25	DITTO Summit 2023 - November 2023	China	Open Science	Presentation
26	EMODnet Open Conference 2023 - November 2024	Belgium	Marine Research	Panel discussion & Poster
27	AGU23 - December 2023	USA	Earth and space research	Presentation
29	ESFRI-EOSC Policy Workshop on "FAIR Data Productivity and Advanced Digitalization" - January 2024	Italy	Open Science	Panel discussion
30	EOSC Winter School - January 2024	Greece	Policy & Open Science	Networking
31	EOSC workshop at Norwegian University of Science and Technology - February 2024	Norway	Policy & Open Science	Presentation
32	DTO Taskforce Workshop for tuning Blue-Cloud data lakes with DTO developments - February 2024	France	Policy & Open Science	Workshop
33	Mission Ocean & Waters Forum - March 2024	Brussels	Policy & Open Science	Posters
34	Oceanology International London - March 2024	UK	Marine research & Industry	Presentation

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
35	2024 Ocean Decade Conference - April 2024	Spain	Marine policy, research & Industry	Joint workshop & booth
36	EGU2024 - April 2024	Austria	Geoscience	Posters
37	EOSC Tripartite Belgium - April 2024	Belgium	Policy & Open Science	Poster
38	IMDIS 2024 - May 2024	Norway	Marine Research	Presentation & Posters
39	EMD 2024 - May 2024	Denmark	Marine Research	Joint workshop & booth
40	Digital Ocean Forum - June 2024	Belgium	Marine Research	Presentation

Table 5: List of third party events that Blue-Cloud 2026 partners attended

5.3. Next Blue-Cloud events

Blue-Cloud will organise 3 annual impact events to highlight the latest developments of the KERs. First discussions took place to organise the first impact event, by the end of 2024, with marine research infrastructures involved in Blue-Cloud 2026, to showcase to other research infrastructures from different clusters the exploitation potential of Blue-Cloud services. At the time of writing, Blue-Cloud consortium is designing a proposal for an event to be co-located with the [Marine User Days](#) in Lisbon 5-6 November 2024, hosted by EUMETSAT and organised by the European Commission, European Space Agency, the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts, Mercator Ocean International and the Copernicus Marine Service.

The remaining 2 editions of the annual impact events are foreseen to take place by the end of 2025, when the V Labs and Workbenches are further developed, and by end of the project, co-located with the final event.

The **Blue-Cloud Hackathon** and the **Blue-Cloud final event**, both relevant activities to promote the Blue-Cloud 2026 KERs, are aimed to be organised during the last year of the project.

6. Publications

Blue-Cloud 2026 published 3 papers and 3 Publications in the IMDIS - INGV MISCELLANEA journal Conference Proceedings (posters - see table below) between M1-M18, from IEEE and Springer publishers. The papers are not only focused on marine research, but also on technology development related to the Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE Cloud Infrastructure (which can be applied not only for marine science). In these cases, the connection with the marine level is based on technology exploration.

N	DOI	Title	Authors	Publisher	Date
1	10.1109/bigdata59044.2023.10386969	Ocean Data Quality Assessment through OutlierDetection-enhanced Active Learning	Li, Na; Qi, Yiyang; Xin, Ruyue; Zhao, Zhiming	IEEE	December 2023
2	10.48550/arxiv.2401.12597	Towards Privacy-, Budget-, and Deadline-Aware Service Optimization for Large Medical Image Processing across Hybrid Clouds	Wang, Yuandou; Kanwal, Neel; Engan, Kjersti; Rong, Chunming; Grosso, Paola; Zhao, Zhiming	Springer	January 2024
3	10.1186/s13677-023-00434-6	Robust-PAC time-critical workflow offloading in edge-to-cloud continuum among heterogeneous resources	Robust-PAC time-critical workflow offloading in edge-to-cloud continuum among heterogeneous resources	Springer	April 2023
5	https://doi.org/10.13127/MISC/80	Blue-Cloud 2026 - Federating European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for Marine Data	Rita Meneses, Sara Pittonet, Dick Schaap	IMDIS - INGV MISCELLANE A journal	May 2024
6	https://doi.org/10.13127/MISC/80	Blue-Cloud 2026 - Federated Data Discovery and Access Service	Dick Schaap (MARIS), Enrico Boldrini (CNR -IIA)	IMDIS - INGV MISCELLANE A journal	May 2024
7	https://doi.org/10.13127/MISC/80	Blue-Cloud 2026 - Virtual Research environment service	Massimiliano Assante, Luca Frosini, Leonardo Candela, Francesco Mangiacapra, Elisa Molinaro, Pasquale Pagano (CNR-ISTI)	IMDIS - INGV MISCELLANE A journal	May 2024

Table 6 Blue-Cloud 2026 papers and conference proceedings by M18

As future plans, Blue-Cloud 2026 aims to keep publishing papers, to keep dissemination of new knowledge and scientific/technical innovation (KPI end of the project is 5).

1.1.1. International Journal of Data Science and Analytics Call for Papers: Special Issue on Data Science and AI in Marine Science and Blue Economy

Blue-Cloud 2026 organised the launch of a Special Issue of the International Journal of Data Science and Analytics on Data Science and AI in Marine Science and Blue Economy, calling for papers on up-to-date high-quality research and innovation results in all areas related to AI, data science, and scientific workflows in marine science. Contributions promoting Open Science and FAIRness were particularly encouraged. Guest editors of the Special issue are Hongsheng Bi, Center for Environmental Science, University of Maryland, College Park Cambridge, United States, and Blue-Cloud partners Leonardo Candela and Pasquale Pagano, CNR-ISTI, Italy, and Dick Schaap, MARIS, The Netherlands.

Launched in September 2023, the call for papers closed in June 2024 and received 12 applications, which at the time of writing are being reviewed. A promotional campaign was run during this period, with a dedicated [news on the Blue-Cloud website](#), continuous social media posts and the news distributed via in Blue-Cloud newsletters and across the consortium.

Figure 33: Promotional banner for the Special Issue of the International Journal of Data Science and Analytics launched by Blue-Cloud

7. Blue-Cloud Training Academy (Campaign #3)

The Blue-Cloud Training Academy is a vital initiative aimed at promoting capacity building to train and guide data providers and ocean observers in the European marine landscape. Its primary goal is to enhance the utilisation of Marine Research infrastructures and marine data repositories, with a strong emphasis on the FAIR principles for data submissions. Additionally, the academy seeks to expand the network of Research Infrastructures among structural data providers. The objectives are:

- **Promote Capacity Building:** Train and guide data providers and ocean observers on optimal use of Marine Research infrastructures and marine data repositories.
- **FAIR Data Principles:** Ensure data submissions adhere to FAIR principles to enhance the quality and usability of marine data.
- **Network Expansion:** Expand the network of Research Infrastructures and structural data providers.
- **Training Modules:** Develop training modules focused on best practices, standards, and services, with a special emphasis on FAIR principles and their implementation.

The academy compiles Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs) on best practices, standards, and services. It prepares comprehensive training webinars and modules around FAIR principles, including the use of BDIs and the Blue-Cloud platform and services.

Three online webinars were organised to promote the adoption of open science practices and were disseminated through various platforms such as Ocean Best Practices (OBPS), the IODE OceanTeacher Global Academy (OTGA), and promoted through the EuroGOOS community and network. The series has not only facilitated knowledge sharing but also contributed to the broader adoption of open science practices in the marine research community.

The details are as follows:

Nr	Title	Number of participants	Training materials	Links
1	FAIR Data Principles 1: Foundational components, best practices, and standards. 26 September 2023 16:00–17:00	264 registrations	https://zenodo.org/records/10001256	https://blue-cloud.org/events/fair-data-principles-1-foundational-components-best-practices-standards
2	Optimising FAIRness of federated data discovery and access service and underpinning Blue Data infrastructure 6 December 2023 10:00–12:00	84 registrations	https://zenodo.org/records/10276224	https://blue-cloud.org/events/optimising-fairness-federated-data-discovery-access-service-and-underpinning-blue-data

Nr	Title	Number of participants	Training materials	Links
3	FAIR Data Principles 2: Making Marine Data FAIR: FAIR assessment of marine data & information	64	https://zenodo.org/records/11070956	https://blue-cloud.org/events/fair-data-principles-2-towards-fair-implementation-profile-marine-data

Table 7: List of webinars organised under the Training Academy

All webinars were organised in collaboration with consortium members (7) and external speakers. The experts were responsible for preparing tutorials, collecting feedback, and supporting the monitoring of participation and the expected impact. Post-event materials were provided to participants to reinforce learning and facilitate ongoing engagement with the topics discussed. Details about the webinars, including the agenda and the content, are as follows:

- FAIR Data Principles 1: Foundational components, best practices, and standards (26 September 2023)** delved into the multifaceted challenges and potential solutions involved in implementing FAIR foundational components. The webinar focused on understanding and adopting the FAIR Principles to effectively translate them into practical FAIR Practices. Participants gained insights into the complexities of "FAIRification," which involves not only the theoretical underpinnings of these principles but also their practical application in real-world scenarios. The session highlighted various strategies to overcome obstacles, ensuring that data management practices are not only compliant with FAIR standards but also optimised for enhanced accessibility, interoperability, and reuse

Time	Session	Presenter
14.00 - 14.10 UTC (16.00 - 16:10 CEST)	Welcome & overview	Sara Pittonet, Blue-Cloud2026 coordinator
14.10 - 14:20 UTC (16.10 - 16:20 CEST)	Interoperability in the marine domain through FAIR best practices and standards	Jay Pearlman (IEEE and Blue-Cloud2026)
14.20 - 14.35 UTC	Process and developments to achieve marine data FAIRness to support Virtual Research	Peter Thijssse (MARIS and Blue-Cloud2026)
14.35 - 14.50 UTC	Practical examples how improved marine data FAIRness supports developers and end-users in current developments in Virtual Research	Alexandra Kokkinaki (NOC UK and Blue-Cloud2026)

Time	Session	Presenter
14.50 - 15.00 UTC	Getting FAIR done: a view from RDA Europe	Najla Rettberg (RDA)
15.00 - 15.15 UTC	Making marine data truly interoperable and reusable: data harmonisation, validation, and qualification from various sources for the creation of streamline data handling for Essential Ocean Variables (EOV)	Simona Simoncelli (INGV and Blue-Cloud2026) or Alessandra Giorgetti (OGS & Blue-Cloud2026)
15.15 - 15.30 UTC	Q&A & next appointments	Sara Pittonet, Blue-Cloud2026 coordinator

Table 8 Agenda of the FAIR Data Principles 1 webinar

2. **Optimising FAIRness of federated data discovery and access service and underpinning Blue Data infrastructure** (6 December 2023) explored information about the Blue-Cloud initiative and more details about the architecture and approach for the Blue-Cloud DD&AS as the core services of the Blue-Cloud ecosystem [Federated Data Discovery & Access Service \(DD&AS\)](#). The webinar was organised with the support of [Ocean Best Practices](#) initiative.

Time	Session	Presenter
10:00 - 10:10	Introduction Blue-Cloud 2026 project	Dick Schaap - MARIS & Blue-Cloud
10:10 - 10:30	Data management and provision by EuroArgo – Argo ocean observing system	Thierry Carval . IFREMER & Blue-Cloud
10:30 - 10:35	Questions & Answers about EuroArgo	All
10:35 - 10:55	Data management and provision by SeaDataNet pan-European marine and ocean data management infrastructure and network	Dick Schaap - MARIS & Blue-Cloud
10:55 - 11:00	Questions & Answers about SeaDataNet	All
11:00 - 11:20	Data management and provision by EMSO ocean observing system	Raul Bardaji - EMSO & Blue-Cloud
11:20 - 11:25	Questions & Answers about EMSO	All
11:25 - 11:45	Architecture and approach for Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service and planned optimisation	Dick Schaap - MARIS & Blue-Cloud
11:45 - 12:00	Overall Questions & Answers and Closure	All

Table 9 Agenda of the webinar “Optimising FAIRness of federated data discovery and access service and underpinning Blue Data infrastructure”

3. **FAIR Data Principles 2: Making Marine Data FAIR: FAIR assessment of marine data & information** (23 April 2024) focussed on some of the recent examples of how Blue Data Infrastructures are advancing towards FAIR assessments and development of FAIR Implementation Profile. It showcased how these infrastructures are incorporating best practices from various projects and initiatives across Europe. A key highlight was the integration of M2M semantic interoperability, ensuring seamless data exchange and understanding between different systems and platforms. By leveraging these cutting-edge practices, Blue Data Infrastructures are not only enhancing data quality and accessibility but also fostering a more collaborative and efficient research environment in marine and environmental sciences

Time	Session	Presenter
16:00 - 16:10	Welcome & introduction: Overview of the Blue-Cloud Data Federation approach	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, IT-TRUST Tjerk Krijger, MARIS
Session 1: Blue-Cloud Common Metadata Profile: state of the art from Blue-Cloud federated BDIs <i>Examples of Blue-Cloud 2026 Data Infrastructures working towards FAIR assessments and FAIR Implementation Profiles for marine data</i>		
16:10 - 16:20	Making EurOBIS Biology metadata interoperable with Blue-Cloud VRE	Katrina Exter, VLIZ
16:20 - 16:30	EMODnet Physics integration with Blue-Cloud	Antonio Novellino, ETT
16:30 - 16:40	EuroArgo semantic artefacts	Thierry Carval, IFREMER
Session 2: M2M Semantic interoperability in Europe <i>Examples of other initiatives in Europe working on FAIR assessment of marine and earth science data</i>		
16:40 - 16:50	FAIR EVA: Bringing institutional multidisciplinary repositories into the FAIR picture	Fernando Aguilar Gómez, CSIC Spanish National Research Council
16:50 - 17:00	FAIR Connect: Open Access publishing platform good practices for professional FAIR-Data stewardship	Barbara Magagna, GO FA Foundation

17:00 - 17:10	Setting up the EarthPortal, the ontology and vocabulary repository dedicated to Earth sciences	Guillaume Alviset, DataTerra
17:10 - 17:20	Insights from EuroGoos Data Management practice	Thierry Carval, IFREMER
17:20 - 17:45	Q&A, closure and next steps	Deniz Karaca, EuroGOOS

Table 10 Agenda of the FAIR Data Principles 2 webinar

In addition, a series of internal webinars were organised by WP3 partners on topics related to data quality and data assessment:

- **Estimating and understanding the ocean heat content change (24 May 2023).** Ocean heat content (OHC) is a measure of ocean warming and is central to the global energy cycle and the other major Earth system cycles. Thus, OHC is a key indicator of climate change. Ocean warming also has extensive impacts and consequences, posing risks to marine ecosystems and human society. In order to better understand this topic, the Blue-Cloud consortium has organised an internal webinar on 24 May 2023 with Professor Lijing Cheng. During this an-hour online event, Cheng showcased the definition and key concepts of OHC and research priorities in a comprehensive presentation. After that, he introduced recent advances in estimating and monitoring OHC change, including data bias correction, quality control, and mapping. These new developments lead to a revised and improved estimate of OHC, which gives important implications to the complementary sea level and the Earth’s energy budget. On the other hand, the presentation provided has also synthesised the recent understanding of ocean heat content changes from inter-annual to multi-decadal scales, from global to regional scales, using observations and models.
- **Data quality improvement for ocean in-situ observations: quality control and duplicate checking (25 May 2023).** In order to deepen this topic and understand its root causes, the Blue-Cloud team organised a webinar on 25 May 2023 with Prof. Zhetao Tan. In this talk, Tan first shows a new automatic quality control system (called CODC-QC) to check ocean temperature and salinity profiles. This system doesn’t assume any data distribution and uses a time-varying threshold to minimise the possibility of mistakenly flagging good data. It works better on different ocean instruments. Using CODC-QC shows more stronger ocean warming rates and helps improve ocean science. Besides, the talk also shows a duplicate checking algorithm (called ‘DNA’ method) to detect potential duplicates in the WOD with more than 20 million profiles, creating a benchmark dataset with duplicate/non-duplicate flags and identifying the physical reasons behind duplication. All these can help improve the data quality of ocean in-situ observations.
- **CORA datasets QC procedures and products (31 May 2023).** The CORa dataset stands as a cornerstone in the Copernicus marine product catalog (INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001), offering comprehensive in-situ temperature

and salinity data. This validated dataset spans from 1950 to year-1, encompassing diverse sources like historical bottle casts, state-of-the-art sail drones, and vessel-mounted thermosalinographs. On May 31, 2023, the Blue-Cloud team engaged in an insightful meeting with Dr. Tanguy Szekely. The goal was to delve deeper into the dataset's specifications, validation methods, and challenges. The discussion covered both the in-situ dataset and its associated objective analysis product, showcasing Blue-Cloud's expertise.

- **Quality control on Argo data: from the automatic tests to the MinMax method (7 June 2023).** In response to the need for rapid data delivery within 12 to 24 hours of a float reaching the sea surface, Argo data undergo automatic real-time quality control tests, albeit with limitations. To enhance data quality, the Coriolis Data Center employs additional methods to detect anomalies missed by these automatic tests. Upon uploading/updating files to the GDAC, they are also added to the Coriolis Oracle database. Subsequently, these files undergo analysis using the MinMax test (Gourrion et al., 2020). This method identifies contaminated profile sections and anomalies caused by sensor drift. Visual verification of resulting alerts is performed using Scoop software, and necessary adjustments are made to the quality control indicators in the Coriolis database. Proposed corrections to the quality flags are then relayed to relevant DACs via automated messages, also accessible on the Ifremer ftp site. The objective is swift removal of erroneous measurements from the data flow. These processes were extensively discussed by the Blue-Cloud team during a dedicated webinar with Dr. Christine Coatanoan on 7 June 2023.
- **EMODnet Chemistry data Quality Control approach, Duplicates check and Products generation (19 June 2023).** The Blue-Cloud has organised an internal training webinar on June 19 2023 with EMODnet's members. In this event, the team delved into EMODnet Chemistry's data Quality Control procedures, covering eutrophication and ocean acidity data across European Sea Basins. Part one of the event explored the "Quality Control loop" involving data originators, managers, and regional sea coordinators, utilising semi-automatic checks and expert insights. The second part focused on duplicate check methods, ensuring the removal of replicate observations. Lastly, the team discussed the methodology for creating gridded climatologies for eutrophication data at various scales in European Seas.
- **World Ocean Database quality control and metadata (20 June 2023).** The World Ocean Database (WOD) is a global initiative led by IOC IODE aimed at openly sharing and consolidating a vast collection of historical and contemporary oceanographic data, including physical, chemical, and plankton profiles, adhering to FAIR principles and rigorous quality control. Hosted at NOAA, WOD encompasses over 18 million profiles of crucial ocean variables sourced from research programs, institutions, scientists, and data centers across 96+ countries. This well-structured, searchable, and metadata-rich database promotes data reproducibility and assures data provenance. Originator data in WOD are openly accessible, potentially receiving DOIs. WOD's metadata empowers ocean data users to select and extract relevant data, while facilitating easy data uploads for international collaboration and equitable data availability. We eagerly seek global partnerships to foster open ocean data sharing, enhance data quality control, eliminate duplicates, improve calibration, standardize metadata, and provide FAIR

analysis-ready data. The benefits of adopting the WOD were explored by the Blue-Cloud team during an internal training led by the ESEB member, Hernan Garcia.

- **Machine Learning to Improve and Support Ocean Data Quality Control (6 July 2023).** The presentation held on 6 July 2023 by Dr. Mohamed Chouai delved into the AWI innovative approach, fusing traditional quality control methods with cutting-edge Machine Learning techniques. He discussed the development of a hybrid system that combines traditional automatic quality control methods with Machine Learning techniques to improve the detection of errors in temperature hydrographic data. His presentation focussed on the UDASH dataset and highlight the system's ability to detect suspect gradient and spike/outlier errors. The multilayer perceptron model achieved remarkable accuracy, surpassing traditional methods in identifying these errors. A live demonstration using the AWI Virtual Machine was also provided to showcase the effectiveness of the ML NN model in detecting profiles that have been changed from bad to good. The user-friendly AutoQC app, which integrates the ML Neural Network model for enhanced detection of problematic profiles was also presented.
- **webODV for the Physical WorkBench (PWB). On 6 July 2023,** the Blue-Cloud team met with Dr. Sebastian Mieruch for an internal training to explore how to integrate the webODV into the project's Physical WorkBench. Dr. Mieruch's presentation focused on a customised version of webODV that facilitates data import, enables connections to private workspaces, supports data sharing, and allows collaborative real-time work on data collections. This functionality will be introduced to foster discussions within BlueCloud's WorkBenches.
- **Copernicus Marine In Situ TAC QC procedure and duplicate check (7 July 2023)** On 7 July 2023, the Blue-Cloud team organised an internal training session with Dr. Delphine Leroy and Virginie Racape (POKaPOK) to explore the technical aspects of data quality control and duplicate detection in the context of marine science. The webinar put a specific emphasis on oxygen, nutrients, and chlorophyll-a data as it aimed to illustrate the meticulous processes employed by Copernicus Marine Services to maintain data accuracy and integrity.
- **[Ocean data quality assessment through outlier detection-enhanced active learning](#)** (29 January 2024) organised as an internal training session and focussed on n ocean and climate research, the importance of global ocean observation initiatives such as Argo, the Global Sea Level Observing System (GLOSS), and the EMSO was emphasised.

7.1. Plans ahead: OTGA training courses

The Blue-Cloud Training Academy has successfully established itself as a key instrument for promoting capacity building in the marine domain. Through its comprehensive training modules, strategic collaborations, and targeted communication efforts, the academy is making significant strides in enhancing the understanding and implementation of FAIR Principles among data providers and ocean observers.

The Training Academy is committed to enhancing our understanding and application of FAIR Principles and Blue Cloud services. In line with this commitment, the Academy will continue to organise webinars focused on these principles, the next one on FAIR data principles being scheduled for the third quarter of 2024 aiming to further discuss FAIR aspects related to data collection.

From the third quarter of 2024 on, **Training courses** will be designed and run to train on the usage of the Blue-Cloud services, namely the VRE, the DD&AS, the Virtual Labs and EOV WorkBenches. These sessions are designed to provide participants with practical insights and hands-on experience in utilising advanced tools and methodologies for ocean observation and data analysis and will be organised in close collaboration with OTGA. This new training opportunity will start in late 2024 with a course on Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment and will be implemented in conjunction with the globally recognized [Ocean Teacher Global Academy](#) (OTGA), a team member of the IEEE BC2026 Partner. The courses will be designed following the Lesson and Module Plan for OTGA Training Courses and enrolled in the [OceanTeacher platform](#) to be distributed as official OTGA courses. Training courses will then remain on the OTGA Moodle platform as a self-paced training course.

1.2. Blue-Cloud’s training academy materials

To share best practices and comprehensive resources that guide researchers in utilising Blue-Cloud services for Open Science in the marine field, the team has developed a series of training materials including factsheets, reports, and videos.

The list of materials developed as of M18 is summarised in the table below.

Type of material	Type of format	Number of materials	Description of the material
VLabs workflows	Report	5	Documents explaining the steps to implement VLabs in the Blue-Cloud VRE, from workflows definition, implementation and testing.
VLabs descriptions	Report	5	Documents explaining scope and services of each of the VLabs
VLabs services	Report	15	Description of the thematic services available via Blue-Cloud and how can users access and use them
VRE description	Report	1	Description of the VRE and the common services available
DD&AS description	Report	1	Overall description of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service (DD&AS)
Blue Data Infrastructures descriptions	Factsheet	8	Description of Description of the Blue Data Infrastructures federating data via the DD&AS
Services videos	Video	7	Videos to present the characteristics of the Blue-Cloud’s main services

Table 11 - training materials developed by M18

All the materials will be accessible through the Blue-Cloud [Training Academy Catalogue](#), the [Training Platform on the project's website](#) and [Zenodo](#). To keep the Blue-Cloud community informed about ongoing developments, additional materials will be created and distributed in the coming months. If necessary, the materials developed by M18 will be updated to include any new advancements.

All the materials developed help achieve the KPIs related to the Training Academy:

2. Number of use-case scenarios supported by the prototype implementation >5
3. VLabs Implementation guidelines, technical requirements, VLabs user Handbook downloaded >200 times

8. Synergies, EOSC & DTO (Campaign #4)

Blue-Cloud is working on the identification of relevant EU and international initiatives connected to the blue economy, marine research, open science and Digital Twin of the Ocean to promote a structured dialogue to align and cluster common opportunities and goals.

The Campaign #4 focuses on outreach activities to enhance the scientific and economic potential and exploitation opportunities of the Blue-Cloud services, demonstrators and applications. The synergies have been classified in 3 main areas:

- *Technical and Scientific*: the identified partnerships contribute to better connecting computing platforms and services on the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service and the Virtual Research Environment;
- *Policy*: the collaboration with the partners involved provides a horizontal contribution to the Blue-Cloud's 2030 Roadmap
- *Communication and Dissemination*: the cooperation revolves around joint communication activities to share the projects' results and reach a broader community.

A list of identified synergies, as of M18, can be found in the table below.

Nr.	Initiative name	Initiative type	Synergy area	Scope of the cooperation
1	AI4EOSC	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific - Communication & Dissemination	To integrate the AI4EOSC and Blue-Cloud platforms to expanding the size of both project communities and their points of access
2	AquaINFRA	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific - Communication & Dissemination	Technical discussions on how to make the data of the two projects interoperable with each other
3	Aquarius	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific	To enrich the data basin of SeaDataNet, EurOBIS and Copernicus, accessible through the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
4	BlueRemedios	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific	To integrate aquaculture data to the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS to enrich the data basin of the WB on Ecosystem-level EOVS
5	Bridge-BS	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific	To integrate data, related to Black Sea, to the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
6	CLIMAREST	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific - Communication & Dissemination	To create a thematic VLab on the Blue-Cloud platform focussed on Restoration data
7	EcoTaxa	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS

Nr.	Initiative name	Initiative type	Synergy area	Scope of the cooperation
8	EDITO	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific - Communication & Dissemination - Policy	Establishment of the DTO taskforce to provide guidance to researchers and policymakers. The cooperation helps to align Blue-Cloud's planned work and activities with DTO developments
9	EMBRC-ERIC	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
10	EMODnet	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
11	EMSO-ERIC	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
12	ENA	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
13	ENVRI-FAIR	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific - Communication & Dissemination	To help improve the FAIRness level of Blue-Cloud's 4 federated RIs, divided over 4 domains - marine, atmosphere, terrestrial, life
14	EOSC Focus	EU-funded project	- Policy	Blue-Cloud aims to provide inputs to the EOSC macroroadmap
15	Euro-Argo ERIC	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
16	EurOBIS	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
17	FAIR-EASE	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific - Communication & Dissemination	To create two thematic V Labs on the Blue-Cloud platform focussed on Marine Omics Observations and Coastal Water Dynamics.
18	GREAT	EU-funded project	- Policy	To provide recommendations for the Blue-Cloud's roadmap
19	ICOS-Marine	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud's DD&AS
20	ILIAD	EU-funded project	- Policy	To provide recommendations for the Blue-Cloud's roadmap
21	iMAGINE	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific - Communication & Dissemination	To enrich the offer of Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE with aquatic AI services and a dedicated AI workbench for developing, testing, and deploying more AI use cases
22	MARCO-BOLO	EU-funded project	- Policy	To provide strategic guidance and direction through the involvement of project partners' into respective Advisory Boards.

Nr.	Initiative name	Initiative type	Synergy area	Scope of the cooperation
23	Plastic Pirates	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific	To develop scripts to standardise and consolidate the Plastic Pirates data, which could be integrated into the Blue-Cloud’s DD&AS
24	PREP4BLUE	EU-funded project	- Policy	To provide recommendations for the Blue-Cloud’s roadmap
25	SeaDataNet	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud’s DD&AS
26	SIOS	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud’s DD&AS
27	SOCAT	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To help federate data from its infrastructure into the Blue-Cloud’s DD&AS
28	WEkEO	Blue Data Infrastructure	- Technical & Scientific	To facilitate the standardisation and access to data, accessible through the DD&AS
29	WorldFAIR	EU-funded project	- Technical & Scientific	To connect the Blue-Cloud’s DD&AS to the WorldFAIR platform to improve FAIRness of data

Table 12 - Synergies established by Blue-Cloud by M18

The cooperation with these initiatives aims to strengthen Blue-Cloud’s position within the EOSC and DTO landscape. These technical synergies enhance the exchange of information between EOSC infrastructures and validate data quality, potentially enriching the digital twin of the ocean data basin. As part of the Synergy campaign, more collaborations with EOSC and DTO related communities and initiatives will be identified, to strengthen Blue-Cloud 2026 position in these fields.

More detailed information about the status of these synergies will be provided in D6.4 “Blue-Cloud Stakeholders engagement and synergies, 1st report”, due in M24 and in D6.5 “Blue-Cloud Stakeholders engagement and synergies, 2nd report” due in M40. Additionally, dedicated factsheets will be prepared by M42 to summarise the main scope of each established cooperation.

9. Main Outreach and dissemination achievements from M1-M18 and future plans (Campaign #1)

9.1. Website

The Blue-Cloud 2026 website is hosted at www.blue-cloud.org, and it is built on the existing platform of the H2020 Blue-Cloud project.

The website currently counts over **56K page views**, and over **40K sessions** from over **16K users**.

During these first 18 months, the website underwent a series of changes and updates to make the user experience more intuitive, easy to use, and appealing. The website revamp included: new information related to the project, the Vlabs, and the workbenches, a dedicated area for the [Training Academy](#), and a new visualisation for the [Communications Kit](#) and [Events](#) pages.

A Single Sign On procedure was implemented to align registration of users across the public website and the Blue-Cloud open science platform on D4Science; this allows for better mapping of Blue-Cloud users, who are asked to register on the public website and provide information on their profile, affiliation, country, gender and other useful details to ensure the correct monitoring of the user base.

The website offers high-quality resources and articles, OA publications signed posted from the project Zenodo community, branded promotional material and multimedia content designed to both promote project results, educate the audience about its usage, as well as inform how the project contributes to address scientific challenges related to the sustainability of the blue sector.

In the coming months, the **Training Academy** area will undergo a **user experience and design revamp**, to ensure maximum engagement and a smooth user experience for the project’s audience. The revamp includes a more sleek design, a new information architecture to easily identify the training materials, the webinars, and the courses, a reorganisation of the training materials with the use of filters for easy findability, and a generally more intuitive look and feel.

9.2. Social Media

Blue-Cloud2026 has inherited an already existing and solid social media community, launched and cultivated by the H2020 Blue-Cloud project. In the past 18 months, the project’s social media follower base has been growing steadily, and as of June 2024 the project has reached a community of **3000+ combined followers** (more than half way to achieve the KPI of 5.000 followers by end of the project). The existing social media community per social media is captured in the Table below.

Channel	Link	Followers as of M18
Twitter/X	https://x.com/BlueCloudEU	1703

LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/blue-cloud-org	1065
Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/@BlueCloudorg	234

Table 13 - Social Media Followers as of M18

Social Media is being used as an instant form of communication with the project’s community members, and potentially interested people or organisation who do not belong to the Blue-Cloud2026 consortium, to help ensure continual visibility of the project’s efforts to disseminate project’s results and developments, like webinars, workshops or general events, but also general announcements, promotion of training materials and Vlab updates.

As of June 2024, Blue-Cloud2026 has produced a total of **3129 total posts** (596 LinkedIn posts, 2429 Tweets, 104 videos uploaded on YouTube). For social media posts that do not include live photos or videos, a custom made banner has been designed to attract immediate attention from our potential audience with an appealing graphic that visually summarises the content of the post.

Figure 34 - Examples of graphic banners for social media

9.2.1. X

Formally known as Twitter, X is being used as the main channel for sharing brief, real time information around the project. As of month 18, the X community has grown to **1703 followers**, seeing a constant increase from the beginning of the project.

Due to the nature of this social media, X is mainly being used to share short messages and updates, live tweeting from events, and brief news with links to the project’s website.

Figure 35 - Examples of posts for X

9.2.2. LinkedIn

The Blue-Cloud2026 LinkedIn account saw a steady increase from M01, gaining 287 followers. The engagement rate of the project’s page saw an increase of 74.6% compared to other similar initiatives, with a high 15% engagement rate, confirming the project’s community as being one of the most active among others.

The project’s visibility on LinkedIn is being enhanced by directly tagging participants, contributors, guests, speakers on specific posts, allowing for more reach among professionals from across the marine and maritime sectors.

Figure 36 - Examples of posts for LinkedIn

To further engage and attract the existing LinkedIn community, the project has implemented the **use of LinkedIn Newsletters**, dedicated informative articles grouped under a common topic, known as “newsletter”, used specifically to inform the project’s audience on Blue-Cloud's Data Federation approach on data harmonisation in collaboration with Blue Data Infrastructures. The LinkedIn Newsletter is used as a way to raise awareness, inform and educate the existing Blue-Cloud2026 audience of the project’s developments, and as a way to promote exclusive content to the project’s LinkedIn community. Currently, **Blue-Cloud2026’s LinkedIn Newsletter counts 359 subscribers.**

NEWSLETTER

Making marine data FAIR

Insights on Blue-Cloud's Data Federation approach on data harmonisation in collaboration with Blue Data Infrastructures.

By **Blue-Cloud 2026**
 1,067 followers

Published monthly
359 subscribers

Figure 37 - LinkedIn Newsletter

Additionally, to further promote the Blue-Cloud2026 services such as the Virtual Research Environment, the Data Discovery & Access Service (DD&AS) and the Data Catalogue, the project’s team has designed branded “carousels”, slideshow-style posts that allow readers to “swipe” across slides and read content, specifically to additionally educate Blue-Cloud2026’s audience on the services the project offers.

Figure 38- LinkedIn Carousels

9.2.3. Youtube

Blue-Cloud2026 inherited the H2020 Blue-Cloud YouTube Channel. Since the 80 videos featured on the platform as of the end of the previous project in March 2023, the channel has grown to **104 videos**, collecting a total of over **40K views so far**.

The videos are grouped into playlists for easy access, and listed as follows:

- Blue-Cloud Training Academy (6 Videos);
- Blue-Cloud 2026 at OSFAIR (3 Videos);
- Blue-Cloud 2026 kick-off meeting (3 Videos);
- Blue-Cloud Interviews (12 Videos).

Figure 39 - Videos available on Blue-Cloud YouTube channel

9.3. Communication Kit & Newsletters

9.3.1. Communication Kit

Concerning communication materials, a complete [communication toolkit](#) was made available to the consortium and the general public. Materials for digital use and for printing are created to promote Blue-Cloud 2026 at physical and online events, and made available on the communication kit page on the website.

A total of 21 documents are currently available on the project’s communication kit. Examples are described in the table below:

Type	Produced by M18
Branding	4 branding materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Logo White ● Logo Colour Positive ● Logo Colour Negative ● Logo Black
Fact Sheets	Cordis Factsheet
Flyers & Brochures	4 items: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Blue-Cloud2026 Brochure (September 2023) ● Blue-Cloud2026 Flyer at the Oceanology International (February 2024) ● Blue-Cloud2026 Brochure (March 2024) ● Blue-Cloud2026 Virtual Labs and Data Lakes Booklet (April 2024)
Posters	7 posters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EMODnet Open Conference Poster (November 2023) ● Blue-Cloud2026 Poster (May 2023) ● A0 format Poster (February 2023) ● 70x10 format Poster (February 2023) ● Oceanology International Poster (February 2024) ● Mission Ocean & Waters Forum Poster (March 2024) ● EOSC Tripartite Event Poster (April 2024)
Press Releases	1 Press Release: Kick Off Meeting (February 2023)
Roll-Up Banners	1 Roll-up Banner (February 2023)
Powerpoint	2 Powerpoint presentations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Blue-Cloud2026 in a Seashell (November 2023) ● Blue-Cloud2026 Official Powerpoint Template

Table 14 - Communication Kit items

Figure 40 - Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs and Workbenches Booklet

9.3.2. Newsletters

Blue-Cloud2026 Newsletters include details about upcoming and past events, as well as achievements and relevant messages for the project’s community. It also features comments and articles published on the Blue-Cloud2026 website.

As of June 2024, 5 Newsletters were circulated to an audience of more than 960 contacts from across the marine research, Open Science, and blue economy communities. Topics included project updates, and promotion of project events such as Training Academy Webinars. The first newsletter issue branded as Blue-Cloud2026 was officially launched in February 2023.

The general open rate of the project’s newsletter issues is between 33% and 39%, which is a good percentage of open issues and shows interest in the content of the project.

In the Table below are shown the Newsletter issues sent so far, which are all available on the [Newsletter](#) sections of the project’s website.

N	Title	Date	Total Opens (%)	Total Clicks (%)
---	-------	------	-----------------	------------------

1	Blue-Cloud2026 To Enhance Open Science For Ocean Protection and Restoration	21.02.2023	38	7.7
2	#WorldOceanDay: Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs for Open Science	15.05.2023	40	7.5
3	Join our next Training Academy webinar + EOSC Symposium & Open Science FAIR in September	01.08.2023	36.73	45.48
4	Don't miss our next Training Academy Webinar - Optimising FAIRness of federated Blue Data Infrastructures	29.11.2023	36.78	28.12
5	Season's Greetings and a Happy New Year!	21.12.2023	30.94	20.87
6	Blue-Cloud2026 6th Newsletter!	02.04.2024	39.70	37.7

Table 15 - Newsletters produced as of M18

10. Timeline of Action Plan from M18

The timelines presented in Figure below outline the main Blue-Cloud communications, dissemination and engagement milestones from M18 till M30 (note that the timeline only includes the most relevant activities). This timing is subject to change, particularly as regards events, and outputs and activities performed by other project WPs.

Figure 41 Communication timeplan from M18 on

The efforts for the next months will be focused on engaging with stakeholders through events, workshops & webinars, as well promoting the latest releases of Blue-Cloud 2026.

11. Conclusion

This deliverable offers a revised and updated version of “D6.1 Communication, Dissemination & Stakeholders Engagement Strategy & Plan”. This document outlines the communication and dissemination activities to be carried out from the time of writing to June 2025 (M30), when a 3rd iteration of this report will be delivered (D6.3 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Education Plan, 3rd release).

The goal for the next period is to further consolidate and broaden the community (expanding the project’s underlying database of contacts) and supporting the uptake of the technology provided by Blue-Cloud. This will be done through a rich mix of actions, including the organisation of webinars, a hackathon, Blue-Cloud 2026 Impact events and, especially, the exploitation of synergies that will be consolidated in the following months, jointly addressing different stakeholder categories.

Last but not least, the W6 team will work closely with WP7 on Blue-Cloud 2026 exploitation plans, but also on the promotion of the strategic Roadmap towards building a federated, digital, marine knowledge ecosystem into EOSC.